

English Teachers' Perceptions and Practices in Implementing Active Learning at Sidama Region Secondary Schools of Ethiopia

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to investigate teachers' perceptions and practices in implementing active learning. The study employed a convergent parallel mixed-methods design. The participants were grade 11th English teachers selected at five public secondary schools in Sidama Region of Ethiopia. They were selected in a single-stage cluster sampling technique. A questionnaire, classroom observation, and an interview were employed to collect data. The questionnaire data were collected from 52 respondents and analysed quantitatively. On the other hand, classroom observations and interview data were collected from the same 8 teachers. They were selected by using criterion sampling giving priority to their qualifications and experience. Interview data was collected to the data saturation point and analysed qualitatively using the grounded theory method. The grand mean value of the questionnaire (4.18) suggested that most of the teachers had positive perceptions of active learning. Nevertheless, their practices (3.00) in implementing the techniques are not up to the requirements. The results of simple linear regression analysis, R Square (=0.087), showed that 8.7% of the implementation of active learning depends on the perceptions of the teachers. This result further suggests that English language teachers need to further develop their awareness of the active learning techniques and their use in delivering most English language lessons.

Keywords: Active Learning; Perceptions; Practices; Constructivism; English Language Teaching

INTRODUCTION

Active learning is a preferable instructional approach as it engages students' learning process and promotes their creative thinking skills (Bakir, 2011). It seeks to closely connect students' learning to the real world (Jacobs & Toh-Heng, 2013). To become lifelong learners, students need learn through active learning (Fadel & Trilling, 2012). Active learning is derived from two basic assumptions. The first assumption is that learning is, by nature, an active endeavour, and the second one is that different people learn in different ways (Sutrisno, 2015). These assumptions imply that active learning offers a range of strategies' preferences that provide opportunities for students with different learning styles. These assumptions imply that active learning is an ideal way in English language teaching. In this case, it can be employed at every stage of a lesson: from getting the students engaged in the topic, actively and consciously taking part in discovering language and rules, to free production (Yahyazade et al, 2014). In active learning classes, a teacher is supposed to be a facilitator and guide in assisting students to learn for themselves (Sequera, 2012). A teacher must make the content meaningful (Autthaporn & Koraneekij, 2016), and select techniques that suit the content, age and students' language proficiency (Jacobs & Renandya, 2021). A teacher also encourages and supports students' learning by providing frequent feedback (Kebede, 2023).

Since the introduction of the modern education system in Ethiopia in 1908, the country's education system has through many reforms. During (1974-1991), the socialist regime introduced a new education reform influenced by the Marxist-Leninist ideology. Soon after, in 1994, the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (FDRE) government (1991-2018) commenced a new education and training policy. The focus of the policy was expanding access to education for all. Despite the reforms, the country's education system continues to suffer from various challenges, such as quality and relevance (Bishaw & Lasser, 2012; Tena & Motuma, 2024). The study conducted by Worku (2025) also examined Ethiopia's educational reforms focusing on access-equity tensions. The researcher found that reforms have set groundwork for increased access though there were notable factors. These are socio-economic challenges, inadequate educational infrastructure, financial constrains, negative cultural perception regarding education for girls.

The current Ethiopian Education Roadmap (2018-2030) was initiated by the Ministry of Education in 2016 (MoE, 2018). This work was started by a series of activities, such as desk review, consultations with stakeholders, field study, and international benchmarking visit to two countries-Vietnam and Malaysia. These countries were selected because of their best performing education system. According to the evaluation report, the majority of the Ethiopian secondary school students (51.1%) perceived the teaching and learning in their respective schools as uninteresting and boring. Also, student engagement in instruction was observed to be very low (pp.26-27). Finally, the roadmap recommends that Ethiopia needs to universalise quality secondary education by addressing these challenges. These challenges need to be addressed by using an effective instructional approach, such as active learning (Freeman et al, 2014).

Following the roadmap, the General Education Curriculum Framework, (MoE, 2020) in general and the syllabus of English language for secondary schools (MoE, 2021) were designed. The framework stresses that implementing active learning is the core teaching and learning strategy. Additionally, the English language textbook for grade eleven is designed to enable teachers to employ a range of active learning techniques. These techniques are discussions, presentations, individual/pair/group work, debates, dialogues, dramatizations, report writings, peer teaching, and scenarios across all units. This context provides an opportunity for teachers to guide instruction using active learning techniques. Such instructional practices lead students to involve themselves in higher-order thinking, such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation (MoE, 2020).

In the current education system of Ethiopia, the English language serves as a school subject from grades one through six. The language is also taught as a medium of instruction at middle and secondary schools i.e., grades seven through twelve. Since the language is used as a foreign language in the country, the opportunity to use the language outside the class is very limited. Studies have disclosed that the status of the English language in Ethiopia is poor in primary and secondary schools (Bachore, 2015; Berhane, 2019). Most Ethiopian secondary school students are frustrated and lack confidence in using the language. As to Kumar Jha (2013), ineffective instructional practices and approaches due to linguistic and non-linguistic impediments contributed to the challenges. Linguistic impediments are faulty methodological approaches, a sloppy curriculum with fewer interactive activities, frequent changes of textbooks, absence of audio-visual teaching, lack of exposure to English outside the classroom, and teaching English as a subject rather than a language. Also, non-linguistic impediments such as time-place-manpower constraints, poor treatment and reward cause teachers to be reluctant to teach. To deal with these constraints, teachers need to familiarise students with active learning by mastering sufficient knowledge and experience (Waniek & Nae, 2017).

Some researchers have conducted studies on active learning perceptions and practices. For instance, Yusuk (2020) investigated the English language teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning in EFL classrooms. The findings showed that teachers positively perceived that active learning had positive effects on instruction. However, its' practices in classrooms are moderately practical. In addition, Cooper et al (2018) explored the influence of active learning practices on student anxiety in large-enrolment classrooms. The findings revealed that three active learning practices, such as clicker questions, group work, and random call can negatively impact students' anxiety levels. The researchers recommended that teachers need to create more inclusive active learning classrooms. Moreover, Devira (2020) conducted a study on the current development of active learning pedagogy in high school English classrooms in Langsa, Aceh, Indonesia. The findings showed that teachers' role and students' engagement in class have not yet been incorporated as active learning principles. Similarly, in Thailand, Nonkukhetkhong et al (2006) conducted a study on the implementation of learner-centered pedagogy and found that teachers failed to practice it in classrooms.

Locally, Biniam (2014) conducted a study on the utilization of active learning in Nifas Lafto Sub-city, Addis Ababa, and Eyob (2014) studied the implementation of active learning in teaching English lessons at Hawassa University. Also, Girma (2013) examined teachers' and students' perceptions and practices of active learning in a Communicative English class at Hawassa University. According to the findings of the above studies, the participants' perceptions regarding active learning were positive. However, the practices were inconsistent due to the large class size, shortage of allotted time, insufficiency of facilities and resources, and lack of readiness to implement it. Furthermore, Amare & Dagne (2020) examined teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning strategies utilisation at Yilmana Secondary School in Ethiopia. The findings of their study indicated that the extent of the teachers' practices of active learning in the school was found to be low. Students' lack of interest in active learning and large class size were reported as the responsible for poor practices of active learning.

The current study differs from the above studies in that none of them were conducted in the current study setting. In addition, none of them were focused on examining the extent to which English language teachers' practices depend on their perceptions of implementing active learning, but the current study did. Moreover, unlike the above studies, the current study addressed important aspects that have to be studied as far as this problem is concerned, i.e., the role of curriculum, syllabus, class size, and materials in implementing active learning in the current study setting. Finally, the issue of perception and practice being dynamic motivated researchers to conduct this study. Since perception is based on motivations, expectations, and personal experiences, different people perceive something differently (Wakefield, 1976). This implies that teachers' perceptions and practices towards active learning can vary with changes in circumstances.

The study's general objective was to investigate English teachers' perceptions and practices in implementing active learning in teaching the English language, concerning teachers of grade 11 at Sidama Region secondary schools. In addition, the specific objectives of the study were (1) to examine English teachers' perceptions towards active learning at Sidama Region secondary schools of Ethiopia; (2) to discover English teachers' practices of active learning at Sidama Region secondary schools of Ethiopia, and (3) to examine the extent to of English teachers' practices of active learning depends on their perceptions at Sidama Region secondary schools of Ethiopia. In line with above mentioned research objectives, the following research questions were formulated. (a) How do English teachers perceive active learning at Sidama Region secondary schools of Ethiopia? (b) How do English teachers practice active learning at Sidama Region

secondary schools of Ethiopia? (c) To what extent do English teachers' practices of active learning depend on their perceptions at Sidama Region secondary schools of Ethiopia?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Active Learning-Perception and Practice

Perception is a psychological process which deals with how an individual recognizes and interprets information. Humans perceive something positively or negatively, that will affect their practice accordingly. It is assumed that positive perception supports the perceived situation, and negative perception opposes the perceived situation. The role of teachers' perceptions is a determining factor in the instructional process. In the context of teaching/learning, perceiving any instructional approach, including active learning, is crucial for implementing it accordingly. Research findings also confirm that there is a strong tie between teachers' perceptions of active learning and their efforts to implement it (Bedilu, 2011). It is supposed that teachers practice instruction in the way they perceive it. In line with this, Elnaga (2013) claimed that different individuals perceive the same thing in different ways. Active learning practices require utilising a range of teaching techniques that engages students in a lesson. Effective active learning practices lead to learning-by-doing where students construct meanings from experiences by engaging in tasks and receiving guidance from teachers. Thus, implementing active learning without properly perceiving it is not a simple task. Through perception, teachers become more aware in reference to the what (concept) and the how (methodology) of active learning techniques (Waniek & Nae, 2017). Therefore, the teachers' perception of active learning becomes more meaningful when they understand the concept positively and practice it properly.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

Active learning is supported by a constructivism learning theory. Cognitive constructivism draws attention to an individual learning process and how a person constructs and develops knowledge through experience (Piaget, 1952). On the other hand, socio-cultural constructivism emphasises the social context of learning (Vygotsky, 1962). The basic assumption of this theory is that students have their own explanations and experiences of phenomena encountered in their everyday lives. Learners continuously encounter new horizons from surroundings when growing up. This entire encounter, in turn, is digested and stored in the memory and becomes knowledge (Murtaza, 2017). This enables students to construct own knowledge, to take responsibility for own learning, and to enhance deep understanding in the lesson at hand (Hartikainen et al, 2019).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Teachers' positive perception towards active learning is very crucial to implement it properly. Teachers also need to be conceptualized, understandable, and experienced with the notion of active learning. On the other hand, practices of active learning require utilizing a range of interactive teaching and learning techniques. Employing these techniques helps students be at a path to critical thinking (Tedesco-Schneck, 2013). With regard to relationship between teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning, perception is seen as a guide to practice and practice is supposed as a test of perception. Teachers can enhance students' commitment by helping them to be attentive, motivated, and interested to participate actively in instruction. To do so, more time is needed for students. Allotting more practice time for student-centred activities improves students' academic achievement (Dagar & Yadav, 2016). It also increases motivation and engagement, develops positive attitudes towards learning, enables better retention of material, and improves academic performance compared to conventional classrooms (Baldwin, 2009). In education, the best perception is informed by the best practice, and best practice should be

grounded in perception. If there is a strong relationship between perception and practices, it leads to successful teaching and learning. This intends impacting students and enacting change (Steadman, 2018). Therefore, the more teachers' perceptions and practices are aligned, the more students' engagement and improved instruction occurred.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study employed convergent parallel mixed-methods design. Convergent parallel mixed method is a mixed method design in which qualitative and quantitative data are collected in parallel, analyzed separately, and then merged (Cohen, 2008). This design is chosen because it involves gathering and analyzing quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, but separately. It also entails comparing or relating the two datasets and then integrating the findings into the interpretation juncture. It also enabled researchers to explore participants' points of view by obtaining rich and comprehensive data in depth as well as by promoting methodological triangulation to investigate the problem under study (Wilson & Creswell, 1996). Methodological triangulation involves the use of multiple methods to study a problem.

Research Setting, Population, and Sampling Techniques

This study was conducted in the Sidama Regional State of Ethiopia. The region is located in south-central Ethiopia and 273 km from Addis Ababa. The regional state consists of five administrative zones. These zones were taken as clusters. Three zones (clusters) were randomly selected from five zones by using random cluster sampling. After identifying cluster centres, the researchers employed a stratified sampling technique to select schools from zones. Accordingly, Allamura and Hallade from Hawassa City, Hula from Southern Zone, and Wotararesa and Manicho schools from Northern Zone were selected. The researchers considered two rationales behind selecting the schools for the study: the schools' location (urban or rural setting) and performance levels. Allamura and Hallade schools are selected from Hawassa City. They are supposed to be the representatives of schools in the city. Their performance level is three. Manicho and Hula schools are selected from district-level towns in two different zones. They are supposed to be the representatives of different districts' town schools. Their performance level is two. Also, Wotararesa School is chosen to represent rural-level schools located at the village level.

According to Dorneyi (2007), single-stage cluster sampling is very important to select some targeted groups of the population (for example, schools) randomly and then to examine all participants in those selected units. According to the Sidama Regional State Educational Bureau of Ethiopia, there are about 130 English language teachers teaching at the grade eleven in the region. Among them, 52 (40%) teachers were selected by using single-stage cluster sampling to respond the questionnaires. Regarding the demographic information of the participants, 42 (80.8%) of the respondents were males and 10 (19.2%) of them were females. Regarding their qualification, 31(59.6%) of the respondents were BA/BEd. Degree holders and 21 (40.4%) of them had MA/MEd. Degree. These reveal that the sample population is inclusive of qualified and experienced teachers. On the other hand, 8 teachers (6 males and 2 females) were also purposively selected to conduct classroom observations and interviews. To this end, criterion sampling was used. This sampling calls researchers to set a specific criterion that should be followed by participants to take part in the study (Nyimbili & Nyimbili, 2024). In line with this, the major criteria used to select teachers to conduct classroom observations and interviews were giving priority to their qualifications and experience. Thus, those who have more teaching

experience and an MA/MED degree holders were selected before others. Finally, the following table presents the demographic information of fifty-two participants (teachers) in the study.

Data Collection and Instrumentation

To collect data, questionnaires, classroom observations, and interview were employed. This enabled the researchers to collect both quantitative and qualitative data and to triangulate them (Cohen et al, 2007; Weyant, 2022). The purpose of the questionnaire was to obtain quantitative data about active learning perceptions and practices. The researchers adapted the questionnaire from (Mulatu & Bezabih, 2018; Taye, 2008; Yusuk, 2020). The sources contain the items relevant to the current study. The structure and content of questionnaire items focus on: importance and benefits of active learning, the role of student engagement, developing learner autonomy, student-mediated, and teacher-directed active learning techniques. The analysis was conducted based on the mean/aggregate result obtained through the questionnaire items. The validity of the questionnaire items was checked by obtaining comments from the research supervisors and the most senior colleagues from the field. The reliability of the questionnaire was checked by measuring its internal consistency by using Cronbach's alpha. According to the Cronbach's alpha Coefficient, the reliability of the items was 0.917. Literature suggests that if the statistical score in Cronbach's alpha is >0.7 , the reliability of the items is acceptable; if it is close to 1.00, it is highly acceptable and can be used (Setyowati et al, 2024; Tasir & Abu, 2003).

Observations and interviews were conducted with the same eight teachers to make the data collection process more efficient. Non-participant classroom observations were conducted. The purpose of observations was to collect data on teachers' practice of active learning techniques. Observation is a useful instrument for obtaining direct information in a natural setting (Duff, 2024). A classroom observation tool was adapted from (Birdwell & Harris, 2022). By using the adapted tool, eight English language teacher classes were observed four times in different sections. A total of 32 periods were observed. Each period lasted for 42 minutes. Interview items were used to triangulate and cross-validate questionnaires and classroom observations data about the teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning. Interview data was collected until no new information emerged. This is called the data saturation point. This point is seen as an important indicator of qualitative data validity, and determines the sample size as well (Kumar, 2010).

Methods of Data Analysis and Interpretation

Both quantitative and qualitative data were analysed separately and discussed jointly. Quantitative data collected through a closed-ended questionnaire were analysed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were calculated for frequency counts, percentages, and means. To determine the mean values of a five-point Likert scale, Nemoto & Beglar (2014) and Yuso et al (2020) cut-off points have been used. The points have been accustomed by subtracting the lowest scale from the highest one, i.e., $5-1=4$. Then, $4/5=0.8$, which was added on each side of the scale. Thus, the cut-off points where the mean value lies determine the majority of respondents' agreement with each item and interpreted as follows: 1.00 to 1.80= strongly disagree; 1.81 to 2.60= disagree; 2.61 to 3.40= undecided; 3.41 to 4.20= agree, and 4.21 to 5.00= strongly agree. Likewise, simple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the extent to which teachers' practice of active learning depends on their perception of active learning. This analysis was used to predict and determine the variation in the dependent variable-practice from the independent variable-perception (Wilson & Creswell, 1996). On the other hand, qualitative data collected through interviews and classroom observation were analysed qualitatively. During the analysis of qualitative data, Ellis et al (1992) grounded theory model was followed. The following table presents a brief excerpt or sample code category of the qualitative analysis.

Table 1
 A Brief Excerpt of Open, Axial, and Selective Coding of Interviews

A. Open Coding: Concepts and Categories					
Perceptions of active learning			Practices of active learning		
No	Concepts	Cat egor ies	No	Concepts	Cat egor ies
01	Student-centered teaching approach	Concepts of Active Learning	17	I emphasize on teacher-centered approach	Experiences on using instructional approaches
02	Engages students in instruction		18	Students need to learn everything from me	
03	Teachers facilitate the lesson at hand		19	I use student centered approach	
04	Students set their own learning goal		20	More than 80% of my instruction is lecturing	
05	Enable students to develop language skills	Importance of active learning	21	My use of a particular approach depends on lesson	Incorporating active learning techniques in instruction
06	Creates opportunities to use the language		22	I practice role-playing in teaching grammar lesson	
07	To express ones idea freely and in confidence		23	I use different techniques when I teach speaking	
08	To improve language fluency		24	The contents guide me what technique to use	
09	To minimize shyness among students		25	I use debates by dividing class into two groups	
10	To give time for teachers to provide feedback		26	By creating real life situations	
11	To make classroom and instruction active	Learner engagement and autonomy	27	I prefer lecturing	Commonly used techniques
12	When I give an activity, they try it well		28	I use question & answer, independent work, group work	
13	I encourage some students who get back		29	I employ pair work, drama, case study & jigsaw	
14	Most students are not interested and motivated		30	I use role-playing and brainstorming	
15	My students prefer to learn through my explanation		31	I use cooperative learning and rarely debates	
16	Students are responsible for their learning				
B. Axial coding: Main categories and their Sub-categories					
Sub-categories			Main categories		
The Importance of Active Learning		Developing Learner Autonomy		Perceptions	
Students' Engagement		Conceptualizing Active Learning			
Experiences on Using Instructional Approaches			Practices		
Incorporating Active Learning Techniques in Instruction					
Most Commonly Used Techniques					
The Extent of Practice Depends on Perception			Perception-Practice Gap		
C. Selective Coding: English Teachers' Perceptions and Practices of Active Learning					

Table 1 includes the three stages of coding procedures followed during qualitative data analysis. During the first stage of coding, i.e., open coding, the obtained data were broken down into units of meaning, and then labelled as words and phrases. Next, during axial coding, the researchers re-examined the main and subcategories from the initial or axial coding. Finally, through selective coding, the researchers found the core category that interlaced the emerging themes and categories. As a result, both quantitative and qualitative datasets were merged during interpretation. The interpretation of the merged data was conducted following a side-by-side comparison approach (Weyant, 2022). Following this comparison approach, the researchers first reported the quantitative statistical results and then discussed the qualitative findings in the results and discussion sections.

Procedures of Data Collection

The data collection process was begun by conducting non-participant classroom observations. This enabled to avoidance of pre-information and doubts that the respondents might get ideas if the process had started with responding to questionnaires. The observations were conducted using the Active Learning Classroom Observation Tool (ALCOT), which was developed by (Birdwell & Harris, 2022). ALCOT was chosen because it directly applies to the problem under study. The tool is designed in a way that helps to collect qualitative data about the practices of active learning. The reliability of the tool was checked by obtaining comments from the review of research supervisors and English language teaching field experts in line with research objectives. A co-observer from each school was invited and took part in conducting the observations. To avoid observer bias and inconsistent result, both observers were made to have the same orientations and trainings on the ALCOT. After collecting data, both observers were made to share the observation results with the observed teachers for member checking-to check for accuracy and validity. Finally, the observers agreed on percentage and reviewed and triangulated the data with reference to the recorded audio. Then, the procedure was followed by collecting quantitative data by using questionnaires. Questionnaires filling have taken 15 to 20 minutes on average. Finally, the interview has taken place through audio recording accompanied by note-taking and was later transcribed into text.

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Hawassa University, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Ref. No. CSSH/57/2023. Also, informed consent was obtained from all participant teachers in the study. The start and end of the recruitment period for this study were from 02/10/2023 to 30/10/2023, respectively. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were assured by removing identifying information. To do so, they were told not to mention their names. In addition, during data analysis, codes were used instead of their real names.

RESULTS

This section deals with the results of teachers' perceptions, practices, and the extent to which the teachers' perceptions towards active learning predict their practices in teaching the English language.

Teachers' Perceptions towards Active Learning

Importance and Benefits of Active Learning

The following table presents the results of teachers' perceptions towards the importance and benefits of active learning in teaching the English language.

Keys: SA-strongly agree; 4. A-Agree; 3. U-undecided; 2. D- disagree; 1. SD-strongly disagree, F-frequency; M. Mean value

Table 2

Teachers' Perceptions towards the Importance and Benefits of Active Learning

No	Item Active learning:	Responses												
		SA		A		U		D		SD		Total		M
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1	increases students' memory capacity to learn English language.	26	50	23	44.2	2	3.8	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	4.33
2	helps students to pass through different stages of learning that lead them to self-discovery and creativity.	19	36.5	21	40.4	10	19.2	1	1.9	1	1.9	52	100	4.29
3	provides students with an opportunity to think and talk about the subject matter under study.	16	30.8	29	55.8	6	11.5	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	4.15
4	has significant contribution in making English teaching/learning effective.	28	53.8	21	40.4	2	3.8	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	4.10
5	can help to address learners with different learning styles.	16	30.8	23	44.2	10	19.2	3	5.8	-	-	52	100	4.40
6	has a great contribution to improve the overall English language skills.	13	25	26	50	10	19.2	2	3.8	1	1.9	52	100	4.13
7	creates opportunities for differentiated instruction.	15	28.8	24	46.2	11	21.2	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	3.87
8	motivates students to learn the English language.	25	48.1	24	46.2	2	3.8	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	3.44
9	enhances students' self-confidence.	29	55.8	18	34.6	3	5.8	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.12
10	decreases frustration, shyness or fearful behaviour of students.	23	44.2	16	30.8	9	17.3	4	7.7	-	-	52	100	4.27

Mean Value: SA= 4.21-5.00, A= 3.41-4.20, UD= 2.61-3.40, DA= 1.81-2.60, SD= 1.00-1.80

For the simplicity of data analysis in the table, we merged the “strongly agree and agree” together in one category, and “disagree and strongly disagree” into another category. As can be seen in Table 2, the responses to items 1, 4 and 8 portray that the vast majority, 94.3%, of the respondents' agreed to the idea that implementing active learning increases students' memory capacity to learn, has significant contributions in making teaching/learning effective, and motivates students to learn the English language. Also, the mean values of the three above items (4.33, 4.10, and 3.44) respectively demonstrated the participants' agreement with the items. Accordingly, 90.4% (M=4.12) of the respondents had positive perceptions that using active learning enhances students' self-confidence.

Regarding the role of active learning in providing students with an opportunity to think and talk about the subject matter under study, 86.6% (M=4.29) of the respondents agreed with the item. Again, 76.9% (M=4.15) of the respondents agreed to the perception that active learning helps students to pass through different stages of learning that lead them to self-discovery and creativity. On the other hand, 75% of the respondents showed their agreement to the items 5, 6, 7 and 10 that employing active learning in the English language teaching classes can help to deal with learners with different learning styles, contribute to improve on the overall language skills, create opportunities for differentiated instruction as well as decrease frustration, shyness or fearful behaviour of students. The mean values (4.40, 4.13, 3.87, and 4.27) respectively confirmed the respondents' agreement with the stated items.

The Role of Active Learning in Student Engagement

The following table shows the results of teachers' perceptions towards the role of active learning in student engagement in teaching the English language.

Table 3
 Teachers' Perceptions towards the Role of Active Learning in Student Engagement

No	Item	Responses												
		SA		A		U		D		SD		Total		M
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
11	creates opportunities to share experiences among students.	27	51.9	20	38.5	2	3.8	1	1.9	2	3.8	52	100	4.33
12	encourages peer learning among students.	25	48.1	20	38.5	4	7.7	3	5.8	-	-	52	100	4.29
13	allows students to practice important social skills such as collaboration and teamwork.	21	40.4	22	42.3	5	9.6	4	7.7	-	-	52	100	4.15
14	creates a sense of community such as friendship and emotional connection in the classroom.	17	32.7	25	48.1	8	15.4	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.10
15	improves students' communication skills.	30	57.7	17	32.7	1	1.9	4	7.7	-	-	52	100	4.40
16	helps students develop life-skills that enable them to lead their lives in schools and their future world of work.	20	38.5	21	40.4	9	17.3	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.13
17	decreases the workload of teachers and saves their time.	18	34.6	18	34.6	8	15.4	7	13.5	1	1.9	52	100	3.87
18	decreases the workload of students and saves their time.	12	23.1	16	30.8	9	17.3	13	25	2	3.8	52	100	3.44
19	gives students more time to spend on tasks.	21	40.4	22	42.3	4	7.7	4	7.7	1	1.9	52	100	4.12
20	involves students in problem solving and thus improves their learning.	23	44.2	24	46.2	2	3.8	2	3.8	1	1.9	52	100	4.27

Mean Value: SA= 4.21-5.00, A= 3.41-4.20, UD= 2.61-3.40, DA= 1.81-2.60, SD= 1.00-1.80

The items in Table 3 are continuations from the previous table. Accordingly, to items 11, 15 and 20, the majority of the respondents, 90.4% agreed and had positive perceptions that active learning creates opportunities to share experiences among students, improves their communication skills, and involves them in problem solving and thus improves their learning. The items' mean values (4.33, 4.40, and 4.27) respectively suggested that the respondents had positive perceptions of the above items. Moreover, 86.6% (M=4.29) of the respondents agreed to the item that active learning encourages peer-learning among students. In addition to items 13 and 19, 82.7% (M=4.15) of them agreed with the items that active learning allows students to practice important social skills such as collaboration and teamwork, and gives them more time to spend on tasks. Also, the mean values of both items (4.15 and 4.12) respectively disclosed the respondents' agreement and positive perceptions of the items. Concerning their perception about active learning in creating a sense of community, such as friendship and emotional connection among students in the classroom, 80.8% (M=4.10) of the respondents agreed. Consequently, to items describing the role of active learning in helping students to develop life skills, decreasing

workload of teachers and students and saving their time, 78.9% (M=4.13), 69.2% (M=3.87) and 53.9% (M=3.44) of the respondents respectively showed their agreement.

Developing Learner Autonomy

The following table presents the results of teachers' perceptions towards active learning in developing learner autonomy in teaching the English language.

Table 4
 Teachers' Perceptions towards Active Learning in Developing Learner Autonomy

No	Item	Responses												
		SA		A		U		D		SD		Total		M
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
21	promotes critical thinking among students.	24	46.2	18	34.6	7	13.5	3	5.8	-	-	52	100	4.21
22	facilitates conditions for students to negotiate ideas, opinions, and information.	19	36.5	21	40.4	10	19.2	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.10
23	offers opportunities for progress in language use among students.	17	32.7	29	55.8	5	9.6	-	-	1	1.9	52	100	4.17
24	enables students to practice language skills so as to become proficient.	26	50	21	40.4	4	7.7	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	4.38
25	enhances the active involvement of students in learning any language lesson.	23	44.2	21	40.4	7	13.5	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	4.27
26	engages students to participate in instruction.	24	46.2	20	38.5	7	13.5	1	1.9	-	-	52	100	4.29
27	needs teachers' facilitation.	27	51.9	21	40.4	2	3.8	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.40
28	enables teachers to provide frequent and immediate feedback to students.	19	36.5	25	48.1	6	11.5	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.17
29	enables students to be independent learners.	19	36.5	26	50	5	9.6	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.19
30	makes students responsible for their learning.	21	40.4	24	46.2	4	7.7	2	3.8	1	1.9	52	100	4.19
Grand Mean													4.18	

Mean Value: SA= 4.21-5.00, A= 3.41-4.20, UD= 2.61-3.40, DA= 1.81-2.60, SD= 1.00-1.80

Table 4 also shows English language teachers' perceptions towards active learning. Accordingly, a large number of the respondents, 92.4% and 90.4% agreed to the items that active learning needs teachers' facilitation and enables students to practice language skills to become proficient, respectively. In addition, 88.8% of the respondents showed their agreement that active learning offers opportunities for progress in language use among students. Concerning items 29 and 30, 86.6% of the respondents agreed that active learning enables students to be independent learners and makes them responsible for their learning. With regard to items 25, 26, and 28, the majority, 84.6%, of the respondents agreed that active learning enhances active involvement of students in learning any language lesson by engaging them in instruction, and this enables teachers to provide frequent and immediate feedback to them. In the meantime, the items' mean values in the above table also disclosed the respondents' positive perceptions of the items. In general, the grand mean value of all 30 questionnaires, 4.18, indicates that the majority of teachers agree with the idea that employing active learning has paramount pedagogical importance in teaching the English language.

The data obtained using interview items also substantiates the teachers' positive perceptions and conceptualizations towards active learning. To this end, four interview items were employed to triangulate and cross-validate previously gathered data using a questionnaire. To interpret the interview data, codes such as Resp1 for Respondent 1, Resp2 for Respondent 2...were used. Through the first interview item, the teachers were asked to respond to their conceptualizations regarding active learning. Accordingly, most of the respondents conceptualised active learning positively. The respondents responded that active learning is an approach/method/strategy/technique that enables learners to engage themselves in the teaching and learning process. One of the respondents responded as follows:

Active learning is an instructional approach that engages students actively in teaching and learning. In an active learning classroom, both the teacher and students are also active. Even the lesson itself is active because it makes students interested doing what the teacher requested them to do (Resp7).

For the second interview item, the respondents were asked to reflect on the importance of active learning. The responses implied that active learning is very important for teachers and students as follows:

Active learning makes students active participants; and makes them to be hard workers. It also makes teachers and students work actively and collaboratively. In English language teaching, active learning creates opportunities to practice speaking; thus, it gradually improves their language knowledge and skills (Resp7).

The other respondent also expressed the importance of active learning as follows:

In terms of the teacher, active learning provides time for the teacher to help and give feedback to their students. In terms of students, it helps them by creating an opportunity to practice language skills and use the language, develop friendships and collaboration, help each other, solve their problems, and actively engage in the instructional process (Resp8).

The third interview item was intended to examine the perception of respondents regarding whether they had relevant knowledge, skills, and perceptions to apply active learning in teaching the English language. Resp1 explained, '...I didn't take any training to employ active learning effectively but through my experience, I try my best.' Resp2 clarified that, 'Although I have a theoretical concept of active learning, most of the time, I face challenges while practicing. Resp3, Resp4, Resp5, Resp7, and Resp8 confirmed that they have the relevant knowledge, skills, and perceptions to apply active learning in teaching the English language. However, Resp6 added the following: 'I am not confident to say fully yes. There are different active learning techniques to be used, and I need further training on these techniques and teaching methods, and strategies.'

The last interview item asked respondents about their understanding of the role of the curriculum, syllabus, textbooks, contents and activities, class size, and resources for implementing active learning. Resp5 responded as follows:

Curriculum is a master copy document for others. Whereas, syllabus is a guide to develop textbooks and teacher guides...; textbook is the major teaching and learning material in the classroom...; lessons and activities are expected to be contextualised in the students' context...; a reasonable number of students in a classroom and accessibility to materials are very important for fully implementing active learning (Resp5).

Resp6 added that depending on their convenience or inconvenience, these issues have an affective or facilitative role in implementing active learning in the teaching and learning process. Thus, the overall interview results showed that most teachers had positive perceptions towards active learning.

Practices of Active Learning Techniques

The following table shows student-mediated active learning techniques in which students take more responsibility for their own learning and the learning of their peers.

Keys: 5. **A**-always, 4. **Fr**-frequently, 3. **S**-sometimes, 2. **R**- rarely, 1. **N** –not at all; **F**-Frequency; **M**- Mean Value

Table 5
 Teachers’ Practices of Student-Mediated Active Learning Techniques

No	Item In teaching English, I employ:	Responses												
		A		Fr		S		R		N		Total		M
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
1	group/pair work	8	15.4	7	13.5	31	59.6	5	9.6	1	1.9	52	100	3.31
2	group discussion	9	17.3	17	32.7	18	34.6	7	13.5	1	1.9	52	100	3.50
3	problem solving	11	21.2	17	32.7	11	21.2	13	25	-	-	52	100	3.50
4	peer teaching	5	9.6	13	25	24	46.2	7	13.5	3	5.8	52	100	3.19
5	independent work	14	26.9	15	28.8	15	28.8	6	11.5	2	3.8	52	100	3.63
6	jigsaw group project	1	1.9	6	11.5	17	32.7	13	25	15	28.5	52	100	2.33
7	cooperative learning	11	21.2	13	25	15	28.8	12	23.1	1	1.9	52	100	3.40
8	dramatization	3	5.8	6	11.5	19	36.5	16	30.8	8	15.4	52	100	2.62
9	language games	6	11.5	8	15.4	22	42.3	14	26.9	2	3.8	52	100	3.04
10	concept mapping	5	9.6	11	21.2	19	36.5	8	15.4	9	17.3	52	100	2.90
11	inquiry learning	8	15.4	11	21.2	24	46.2	8	15.4	1	1.9	52	100	3.33
12	role-playing	6	11.5	9	17.3	18	34.6	17	32.7	3	3.8	52	100	3.00

Mean Value: A= 4.21-5.00, Fr= 3.41-4.20, S= 2.61-3.40, R= 1.81-2.60, N= 1.00-1.80

Table 5 portrays the frequencies of student-mediated active learning techniques used by English language teachers. As can be seen in the table, 32.7% and 28.8% of the respondents confirmed that they frequently use problem solving and independent techniques respectively. Consequently, 59.6% of the respondents confirmed that they sometimes employ group/pair work followed by peer teaching and inquiry learning (46.2% each), language games (42.3%), dramatization and concept mapping (36.5% each), group discussion and role-playing (34.6% each), jigsaw (32.7%), and independent work and cooperative learning (28.8% each). In general, the mean values of the items in the above table showed that the respondents always, frequently and sometimes practiced active learning techniques in teaching the English language to grade eleven.

Practices of Teacher-directed Active Learning Techniques

The following table shows teacher-directed active learning techniques in which the teacher is the primary deriver of instruction in teaching the English language.

Table 6
 Teachers’ Practices of Teacher-directed Active Learning Techniques

No	Item In teaching English, I employ:	Responses												
		A		Fr		S		R		N		Total		M
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
13	critical thinking motivators (puzzles/ paradoxes)	4	7.7	5	9.6	27	51.9	13	25	3	5.8	52	100	2.88
14	demonstration	8	15.4	10	19.2	20	38.5	6	11.5	8	15.4	52	100	3.08
15	fish bowl	2	3.8	6	11.5	14	26.9	11	21.2	19	36.5	52	100	2.25
16	lecture /explanation	22	42.3	18	34.6	5	9.6	4	7.7	3	5.8	52	100	4.00

17	brain storming	14	26.9	15	28.8	16	30.8	6	11.5	1	1.9	52	100	3.67
18	question and answer	28	53.8	12	23.2	10	19.2	2	3.8	-	-	52	100	4.27
19	panel discussion	3	5.8	5	9.6	13	25	23	44.2	8	15.4	52	100	2.46
20	project work	2	3.8	5	9.6	15	28.8	15	28.8	15	28.8	52	100	2.25
21	debates	-	-	8	15.4	23	44.2	15	28.8	6	11.5	52	100	2.63
22	field trip	-	-	4	7.7	8	15.4	9	17.3	31	59.6	52	100	1.71
23	discovery learning	2	3.8	9	17.3	9	17.3	22	42.3	10	19.2	52	100	2.44
24	case study learning	1	1.9	9	17.3	21	40.4	12	23.1	9	17.3	52	100	2.63
Grand Mean														3.00

Mean Value: A= 4.21-5.00, Fr= 3.41-4.20, S= 2.61-3.40, R= 1.81-2.60, N= 1.00-1.80

Table 6 also presents the frequencies of teacher-directed active learning techniques used in teaching the English language. As can be seen, 53.8% of the respondents responded that they always employ the question-and-answer technique. The other, 42.3% and 34.6% of the respondents responded that they always and frequently practice the lecture/explanation technique, respectively. Consequently, 51.9% of the respondents replied that they sometimes use critical thinking motivators such as puzzles/ paradoxes, followed by debates (44.2%), case study learning (40.4%), demonstration (38.5%), and brainstorming (30.8%) techniques. On the other hand, 59.6% and 36.5% of the respondents confirmed that they do not at all use the field trip and fish bowl technique, respectively in teaching the English language to grade eleven. The grand mean value of all 24 items, 3.00, shows that most of the teachers use the above active learning techniques sometimes in teaching the English language.

Data obtained through classroom observation also confirms the above result collected by the questionnaire. The observed classroom teachers in different sections often practiced techniques such as group/pair work, brainstorming, question and answering, discussion, individual/independent work, and lecture/explanation. Next to that, techniques such as problem solving, project work, case study learning, cooperative learning, peer teaching, demonstration, and concept mapping are occasionally used. However, inquiry learning, role-playing, panel discussion, critical thinking motivators, language games, and fish bowl techniques were never used by any of the observed teachers.

The eight teachers whose classes' observed were also interviewed to reflect on their experiences of using different instructional approaches and techniques in teaching the language. In response, 4 (50%) of the respondents reflected that, most of the time, they use lecture/explanations. The other, 3 (37.5%) responded that, most of the time, they prefer to use active learning techniques. The remaining, 1 (12.5%) responded that, depending on the lesson at hand, they use both teacher-centred and active learning alternatively in teaching the English language to grade eleven.

Active Learning Practices Depend on Perceptions

To predict the extent to of teachers' practices of active learning depend on their perceptions, simple linear regression is used. Simple linear regression is a type of regression that involves one independent variable (teachers' perceptions towards active learning) and one dependent variable (teachers' practices of active learning). The aggregate value of 30 items of perceptions and 24 items of practices of active learning were used to compute the analysis by using SPSS version 25. The following table portrays the results of the extent of teachers' practices of active learning depend on their perceptions in teaching the English language.

Table 7

The Extent of Teachers' Practices of Active Learning Depend on Their Perceptions
 Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.294 ^a	.087	.068	13.7	.087	4.644	1	49	.036

Keys: a. Predictor: (Constant), teachers' perception, b. Dependent variable: classroom practices

As shown in Table 7, a linear regression equation predicted the new value of the dependent variable (teachers' practices of active learning) and the independent variable (teachers' perceptions towards active learning). The statistical significance at the 95% confidence level was 0.036. In the table, the - result of the regression analysis, demonstrates perception ($R = .294^a$) and practice ($R = 1$). The extent to which teachers' practice of active learning depends on their perception was observed in the simple linear regression analysis model, which is symbolised by R Square= (.087). This shows that 8.7% of the teachers' active learning practice depends on their perception of implementing active learning. The other 91.3% of teachers' active learning practice were predicted by unmeasured variables, such as challenges, that were not considered in the regression equation.

Discussion

Teachers' perceptions towards active learning

This sub-section discusses the results of teachers' perceptions towards active learning in line with the first objective of the study. The section's discussion focuses on the importance and benefits of active learning, the role of active learning in student engagement, developing learner autonomy, and teachers' conceptualizations of active learning.

Importance and Benefits of Active Learning

The first major finding of the study was the importance of active learning in helping students understand the subject under study. This result is consistent with the findings of (Desalegn, 2014). According to this finding, implementing active learning facilitates the exploration of the meaning of the subject being studied. Learners must be given frequent opportunities to deal with new information, experiences and challenges using their past experiences without the dominance of a teacher. During this time, the learners are expected to feel free and accepted. Also, Prince (2004) stresses the pedagogical benefits of using active learning, such as improving critical thinking skills among students and increasing retention and transfer of new information. It also improves motivation and interpersonal skills. The consistent results of the study conducted by Paris (2017) also showed that hands-on, integrative, and collaborative active learning experiences lead to high levels of student achievement and personal development. In addition, active learning motivates students by developing their self-confidence, and decreasing frustration, shyness and fearful behaviour. Accordingly, the findings of other studies were also in agreement with this study's results and revealed that active learning can positively affect student motivation (Owens et al, 2017), and that the overall impact of motivation moderates key learning characteristics such as attention and memory consolidation and promotes self-confidence (Cavanagh et al, 2021).

The Role of Active Learning in Student Engagement

Regarding the role of active learning in engaging students in instruction, the findings of this study are also consistent with the findings of (Munna & Kalam, 2021). The findings disclosed that engaging students in instruction creates opportunities for them to develop creativity and foster

productivity. Teachers must ensure that students' engagement in cognitive, behavioural, and emotional connections to their learning aspects (Christenson et al, 2012). Students' engagement is a visible descriptor of motivation (Martin, 2012; Reeve, 2012) and a predictor of motivation (Pekrun & Linnenbrink-Garcia, 2022). At the classroom activity level, students' engagement concerns their involvement in a specific activity or task in class, and the outcome sought is learning (Philp & Duchesne, 2016). Lack of student engagement affects students' academic capabilities and influences their social functioning. A high rate of student disengagement leads to low academic achievement, high dropout rate, high unemployment, social exclusion, low income, crime engagement, and health issues (Munna & Kalam, 2021).

Developing Learner Autonomy

Developing learner autonomy is very important for taking charge of one's learning. About this, Najeeb (2013) discusses three basic pedagogical principles that underlie autonomy in language learning as learner involvement, learner reflection and appropriate use of the target language. The notion of learner autonomy also implies that language learners can freely apply their knowledge and skills inside and outside the immediate context of learning. This means that once developed, autonomous learning extends beyond the school context. Independent language learning refers to a context or setting in which language learners develop skills in the target language (Wright, 2005). Therefore, employing active learning develops students' autonomy and ability to learn by giving them greater involvement and control over their learning. This means that students are better able to continue learning, even if they have left school. Thus, it is very important to instruct students to have a purpose in their learning, to believe in their capability, to take responsibility for their learning, and to seek to understand text (Taylor & Parsons, 2011).

Teachers' Conceptualizations of Active Learning

The findings of the study also disclosed the participant teachers' positive conceptualizations towards active learning. These were examined by detecting their conceptualizations of having relevant knowledge and skills, and the role of issues such as curriculum, syllabus, teacher guide, and students' textbook in implementing active learning. These conceptualizations are in line with the prior literature references, such as (Saavedra & Steele, 2012; Stoll et al, 2006). Thus, understanding the role of instructional materials is very important to help achieve desired learning objectives, to facilitate the teaching and learning process, and to encourage active learning. These findings are also in line with the research findings of (Bušljeta, 2013). According to him, the purpose and role of teaching and learning materials do not only consist of making the educational process more attractive and interesting, but also of encouraging active learning, the development of different skills, and the adoption of desirable values and attitudes in students. It is difficult to achieve this goal without the proper utilization of these instructional materials.

Practices of Active Learning

This sub-section discusses the results of teachers' practices of active learning in line with the second objective of the study. The section's discussion focuses on discovering English teachers' practices of active learning in teaching the English language to grade eleven. The findings of the study suggested that teachers failed to practice a range of active learning techniques. They rather frequently practice some techniques, such as group/pair work, brainstorming, question and answering, discussion, individual/independent work, and lecture/explanation techniques. These findings are in agreement with the findings of (Mulatu & Bezabih, 2018; Taye, 2008). Their findings reported that English language teachers frequently employ techniques such as lecture/explanation, discussion, individual and group work in their instruction. On the other hand, teachers failed to practice techniques that can engage students to develop critical thinking skills though they have been emphasised in the education policy and documents. In line with this, Telore & Damtew (2023) reported that the effective implementation of active learning in

Ethiopian schools is in question. In addition, Berhanu (2013) and Teshome (2013) also showed that, however, it was found that teachers seem to have positive perceptions towards active learning; they did not properly practice it during classroom instructions. According to Amenu (2005), the dominant use of the conventional lecture method of teaching hinders most teachers not to implementing active learning.

Active Learning Practices Depend on Perceptions

This sub-section discusses the results regarding the extent of English teachers' practices of active learning depend on their perceptions of active learning in line with the third objective of the study. To this end, the aggregate results of the questionnaire (perceptions-independent variable and practices-dependent variable) and classroom observation data were used. Teachers' perception of active learning is supposed to match their practices in the classroom; however, the regression model of the questionnaire depicted that teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning was poor. Since the variation (R^2) which is explained in the dependent variable (practices) by the independent variable (perceptions) is 0.087, i.e. less than 0.1, their magnitude power of goodness of fit was a poor fit (Dorneyi, 2007). This finding suggests that there is a weak relationship between teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning. This finding is consistent with the findings of (Mebratu & Woldemariam, 2018). Their findings depicted that the teachers' perception influenced their practice of active learning in the classroom by 3.0%. However, the remaining 97.0% was predicted by other variables, such as challenges preventing teachers from practicing active learning.

Different studies have reported the challenges teachers face to get engaged their learners in active learning, such as teachers' feelings of uneasiness and lack of confidence, being non-resistant to conventional teaching approach, lack of self-confidence to change their teaching styles, lack of workshops to urge them to use active learning (Bahanshal, 2013; Bulbula et al., 2022). In addition, students' prefer to learn through lecture because active learning can increase their anxiety (England et al, 2017). It has been suggested that the students' anxiety is reduced when they work in groups. Moreover, inability to cover as much content in the time available, large class size, and lack of materials are the major drawbacks to implement active learning properly (Sutrisno, 2015).

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that most of English teachers at Sidama Region secondary schools had positive perceptions towards active learning. This was confirmed from the participants' response to a questionnaire and an interview. Regarding the practices of active learning, English teachers' inconsistent use of active learning techniques was seen. This showed that majority of English teachers failed to utilise a range of active learning techniques in teaching the language. The challenges contributing for inconsistent practices of active learning were lack of successful professional development programs, lack of student motivation, lack of textbook and large class size. Due to these challenges, English teachers' perception of active learning influence on practice was a poor fit. Thus, the study suggested that there was a gap between English teachers' perceptions and practices of active learning in teaching the English language. In sum, this study contributes to the growing area of active learning by enhancing teachers' practices and leads to improved instruction and students' engagement.

Recommendations and Future Research

In this study, it was found that English teachers failed to practice active learning techniques successfully. To boost the teachers' practices of active learning, teacher training and professional development programs need to be strengthened. These programs need to focus on training pre-service and in-service teachers to successfully implement active learning. Also, each

school/English department should bring English language teachers together and facilitate situations in which they discuss the implementation of active learning. School/department can do this by prioritizing active learning as one of its Professional Development (PD) needs. Finally, English teachers should give emphasis to interactive instructional activities. They need to provide input and allow time for students to practice and understand instruction through active learning. This, in turn, enables students to develop the culture of active learning practices and bridges perception-practice gap. The researchers of this study would like to suggest two possible future areas of research. The first one is exploring students' interest and motivation to engage in instruction. The second one would be investigating the exam wash-back effect in implementing active learning in English language teaching classes. In Ethiopia's context, most of the time, the English language examination gives a lot of attention to grammar, vocabulary, and reading lessons. Due to this, the instruction process ignores other skills such as listening, speaking, and writing.

Limitations

The study had some limitations apart from the above significances. The first limitation was the inclusion of a small sample size: five schools and fifty-two participants. The second one was that the study was conducted only at grade eleven. The final limitation was conducting classroom observation and interviews with only eight participants. It could have been difficult and time-consuming if all fifty-two samples had been included to do. Future research may consider involving a broader range of schools and participants to provide a more holistic view.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that there is no competing interest to disclose in this work.

Ethics Statement

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Hawassa University, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Ref.No. CSSH/57/2023. Also, Informed Consent was obtained from all participants (teachers) in the study.

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